

TALENTED, YET NOT CLEARLY UNDERSTOOD INVESTIGATING LANGUAGE BARRIERS OF INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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This research data and interview were taken from the AJOU University in Tashkent

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Abstract. *Language barriers significantly affect the academic and social interaction of international students in multinational universities. This study explores the challenges encountered by international students in Uzbekistan, with a focus on Ajou University in Tashkent covering linguistic difficulties and their influence on academic performance and cultural adaptation. A mixed-method approach was adopted, combining surveys of 13 international students with in-depth interviews. To analyze and address the research questions provided in this study, The Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) developed by Albert Bandura offers a robust framework. Research findings revealed that inadequate proficiency of international students in Uzbek and Russian, combined with limited institutional support and not widely integrated English Language within the Campus environment, exacerbates students' difficulties in communication and learning. The study highlights the need for tailored language programs for international students and support systems to foster inclusivity and improve their experiences in Uzbekistan's higher education landscape.*

Keywords: *international students, Uzbekistan, Ajou Community, language efficiency, multinational universities.*

Introduction

In today's increasingly globalized and developed world, higher education institutions are welcoming a growing number of international students. While this trend enables academic and cultural exchange, it also presents challenges, particularly in regions like Uzbekistan, where educational institutions are in the process of adapting to globalization. Among the most pressing issues encountered by international students is the language barrier, which has profoundly affected their academic success, social integration, and overall well-being within their academic careers. Uzbekistan, as a constantly growing hub for multinational universities, offers a unique context for studying this issue. The linguistic diversity of the country, where Uzbek, Russian, and English often coexist, creates not only opportunities but also obstacles for international students. Those with limited proficiency in these languages may struggle to fully engage with academic content and local communities. Despite the increasing enrollment of international students in Uzbek universities, research on their linguistic challenges remains relatively sparse. According to the statistics at the beginning of the 2022/2023 academic year, the number of foreign students studying at higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan amounted to 5 thousand people. The number of foreign students studying in higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan by years:

2017/2018 academic year - 1.3 thousand people

2018/2019 academic year - 2.7 thousand people

2019/2020 academic year - 3.6 thousand people

2020/2021 academic year - 4.2 thousand people

2021/2022 academic year - 5.1 thousand people

2022/2023 academic year - 5 thousand people

According to the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, as of January 1, 2021, the number of citizens of Uzbekistan studying abroad amounted to 85.9 thousand people. ([stat. uz](#))

These students bring diverse perspectives, cultural richness, nationwide collaboration, and unique experiences that enrich the academic environments of the host institutions. The recent survey states that China leads the list of countries with the highest number of students studying abroad, with over 1 mln students enrolled in foreign institutions. India follows with 621,600 students and Uzbekistan ranks third, with 150,500 students pursuing their studies abroad, showcasing the country's increasing interest in global academic opportunities. ([daryo. uz](#)) However, along with these benefits, international students often encounter significant challenges and sometimes even troubles when adjusting to a new academic and social setting. Among these challenges, language barriers stand out as one of the most pressing issues of today among international students.

For many foreign students, limited proficiency in the host country's native language or even in the medium of instruction can create obstacles in both academic and social interactions. Classroom discussions, collaborative projects, extracurricular activities, casual conversations among peers, and most importantly interactions with university staff often become sources of stress rather than opportunities for engagement. This language gap not only affects their academic success but also hinders their ability to build meaningful relationships and participate fully in campus life.

This paper investigates how language barriers bring about overwhelming, sometimes never-ending, relatively bad experiences for international students in multinational universities in Uzbekistan, particularly Ajou University in Tashkent which has been chosen to do in-depth research in. Drawing on interviews with 13 international students (10 of them are currently studying at AJOU University in Tashkent and another 3 are former AJOU local students who have been transformed into Ajou Main Compas in Korea) the study sheds light on how these challenges affect their social integration and academic performance. Furthermore, it proposes a potential solution: the establishment of a student-led initiative, “Ajou Community” aimed at offering support to international students and encouraging staff members to enhance their communication skills in the language that has been chosen to speak mostly within compass. By addressing these issues, universities can foster a more inclusive environment that benefits both local and international students.

Literature Review

Language skills significantly influence an individual's ability to learn and grow, serving as a crucial tool for exchanging knowledge and managing thought processes (Binder & Smith, 2013). “We argue that conversation is easy because speakers and listeners automatically align with each other at different linguistic levels (e.g., sound, grammar, meaning) which leads to alignment at the level of interpretation” (Garrod, S., Pickering, M.J. (2013)). It provides a broad overview of how perception and action are connected, stressing the direct connection between the two. Specifically, it explores one key outcome of this association: imitation (Dijksterhuis, A., Bargh, J.A.). If communication research applies methodological triangulation to its data and questions and covers a process for building on empirical insights, it can start to be clear of the uncertainties that come with human interaction (Giles, H., Coupland, N., Coupland, J.). This

alignment process is apparent in the repetitive patterns seen in dialogue across different levels. It is driven by both local priming mechanisms and broader processes of routinization. When considering language proficiency, the primary focus is on the communicative aspect of language (Baker, 2001). In the past five decades, bilingual education programs involving members of national minorities have become a focal point of discussions surrounding political, social, and economic issues. Education serves as a crucial platform where two languages frequently intersect (Vlasta Hus, Tina Hojnik). So far, identifying oneself with a nation has been sufficient to sustain a nation-state. However, in today's context, there is a growing need for a stronger sense of ethnic identity, which includes national identity and fostering attitudes toward members of other national communities (Mikolic, V. G). This is because effective communication skills play a crucial role in evaluating a person's ability to succeed both socially and academically (Young, Sercombe, Sachdev, Naeb, & Schartner, 2013). Consequently, fluency in a language plays a profound role in achieving successful integration and reducing cultural adjustment challenges (Andrade, 2006). Fluency in the local language is a key factor in the process of adapting to a new environment.

The process of adapting to a host country's culture often leads international students to modify their eating patterns (Edwards, Hartwell, & Brown, 2010). Research suggests that cultural integration can result in less healthy dietary habits, influencing what foods are chosen, how meals are consumed, and overall physical health (Brittin & Obeidat, 2011; Papadaki et al., 2007; Winham, 2009). Previous research suggests that moving to the United States often leads to changes in eating habits, which can have negative health implications such as weight gain and the development of chronic diseases (Satia-Abouta, Patterson, Neuhouser, & Elder, 2002; Winham, 2009).

An important factor in mastering a new language is the degree of self-esteem possessed by an international student (Jackson, Ray, & Bybell, 2013). The more people talk and interact with the local people the more they become proficient in the language (Yoon & Portman, 2004). It is the culture of being afraid to speak that makes people confident in speaking a second language. Such a cultural divine approach involves people exchanging words and at the same time making mistakes (Clément & Bourhis, 1996). This is consistent with findings from another study, which showed that international students with higher levels of English proficiency and communication effectiveness experience less perceived embarrassment and anxiety and feel less self-conscious about their accents or ethnic backgrounds (Barratt, 1994). “International EAL students encounter various challenges associated with access to social interactions, if any, participating in such social interactions meaningfully (Pritchard, R., and Skinner, B. (2002)), a sense of isolation, financial burdens (Li, R., and Kaye, M. (1998)), overt and covert racism and stereotypes (Guo, Y., and Guo, S. (2017)), and a lack of requisite academic language skills required for successful academic work” (Robertson, M., Line, M., Jones, S., and Thomas, S. (2000)). Globalization has made international students experience different cultural aspects. The change in environment has however depicted challenges in these students from illnesses like depression as stated in literature works from scholars like Parr, Bradley, and Bingi (1992). It has since been established that when people migrate to other nations, they face stressors and challenges especially when they intend to return to their home countries after staying for a longer time (Sherry et al., 2010). In research, it has been established that students from other countries seek their fellow students on how to go about their assignments instead of talking to their superiors (Leong & Sedlacek, 1986). Nonetheless, seeking advice is quite different for

International students who rely on their tutors since many do not know about how society operates.

Research Method

Research Questions and provided Theories

In the present study, we did interviews with 13 international students who are currently studying at Ajou University in Tashkent and in the Main Campus located in Korea and came up with some common questions and expected theories that can clarify their real-life experiences in a more detailed form. Our work was underpinned by the following three main research questions:

Question 1: What are the primary language barriers faced by international students at Ajou University in Tashkent both in academic and social settings?

Question 2: How do language barriers influence international students' academic performance, social integration, and overall well-being?

Question 3: How do they handle group assignments with local students or students from other linguistic backgrounds?

Question 4: How well do university staff (e.g., in the admissions office, libraries, cafeterias) understand and respond to students speaking English or other foreign languages?

Question 5: What suggestions would international students give to improve language accessibility at the university for future international students?

Question 6: What methodologies or institutional support systems can effectively address the challenges posed by language barriers to enhance inclusivity and cohesion on campus?

To analyze and address these research questions, “*Social Cognitive Theory (SCT)*”, developed by Albert Bandura, provided a robust groundwork. One of the seminal sources for understanding SCT is Bandura's book, “*Social Foundations of Thought and Action: A Social Cognitive Theory*” (1986), (SCT) where he elaborates on concepts like observational learning, self-efficacy, and the integration of personal, behavioral, and surrounding factors. It focuses on how people learn and adapt through observation, self-regulation, and social interaction, making it particularly relevant for analyzing the interplay between international students and their campus environment. Additionally, his article, “*The Evolution of Social Cognitive Theory*” (2005), (The SCT) provides an in-depth historical and theoretical perspective on its development. After doing some research on this we formulated the following theories for this study:

Theory 1: SCT emphasizes the role of “*environmental factors*” in shaping behavior. In this sense, the campus environment, including the prevalence of native-language interactions among other students and university staff and teaching methods, can either exacerbate or alleviate language barriers. By assessing these factors through interviews and observations, and launching different incentives to optimize the language proficiency of campus workers, the study can identify specific triggers of language-related challenges.

Theory 2: The theory highlights the concept of “*self-efficacy*”, or an individual's self-assurance in their capacity to succeed in particular circumstances. Language barriers can negatively impact students' self-efficacy, leading to anxiety and reduced participation. In light of this, let us now proceed to focus on the impact of language proficiency on an individual's ability to learn and develop in society and even the economy. Let us not forget that in the case of language acquisition, the motivational aspect related to communication is the most relevant (Baker, 2001). One of the major reasons for this is that effective interaction is a critical parameter when assessing the integration capability of an individual in society and academics

including the performance of an individual (Sds. Young, Sercombe, Sachdev, Naeb, & Schartner, 2013). Therefore, we can say that there is a direct relationship between language fluency the level of mobility, and the trauma felt in a new environment (Andrade, 2006). The process of adjusting to a new culture would not be swept away without proficiency in the core language of that new culture.

Theory 3: SCT concludes that behavior can be modified through *modeling and reinforcement*. This insight can motivate to creation of strategies for addressing language barriers, such as peer mentoring programs, language workshops, or inclusive campus policies. Interventions designed with these principles in mind can foster a supportive learning environment and improve social cohesion.

Research Design

This study employs “a *qualitative research methodology*”, using semi-structured interviews to collect data from chosen people. This approach has been selected specifically to gain in-depth insights into the real-life experiences and challenges faced by international students at Ajou University in Tashkent. The qualitative aspect of the research allows for the thorough exploration of personal narratives, enabling a deeper understanding of the language and cultural barriers these students encounter during their academic lives.

Participants

The study focuses on 13 international students from diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds who are currently enrolled at Ajou University in Tashkent and on the main campus in Korea. All of them are studying in different faculties with various years of acceptance. These participants were selected through *purposive sampling*, ensuring they represent a range of academic programs, levels of language proficiency, and years of study. This diversity helps to capture a comprehensive view of the difficulties encountered by international students.

Data Collection

The main data collection tool is “*semi-structured interviews*”. This format allows for open-ended questions of different kinds while maintaining a focus on the research objectives. Key themes include:

1. Academic challenges caused by language barriers.
2. Social difficulties stemming from linguistic and cultural differences.
3. Existing coping mechanisms and gaps in institutional support.

Each interview lasts approximately 10-15 minutes and is conducted in English or a language preferred by the participant. Responses are recorded with the participant’s consent for accuracy and detailed analysis. Also with the allowance of the participants the filmed video will be posted on all social media platforms of Ajou University to raise the awareness of everyone working and studying there.

The interviews also incorporate *direct quotes* from participants to highlight real-life experiences. For instance:

- "It’s tough when professors assume you can understand everything when they speak their native language."
- "I often feel socially isolated because it’s hard to join in conversations when I don’t know the slang or cultural references."
- "I wish there were more structured language support programs or events to help us connect with local students."

These quotes bring authenticity to the research and help illustrate the pressing issues faced by international students along with some practical solutions to address these confrontations.

Data Analysis

The data accumulated through interviews is analyzed using “*thematic analysis*” which involves transcribing the interviews, gathering and analyzing the data, and pinpointing common patterns. Direct quotes are grouped under each theme to provide context and emotional depth to the findings.

Creation of a Support Club

Based on the research findings and in-depth analysis, a student-run support initiative called "Ajou Community" will be established to address the challenges identified in this study. The club will aim to:

1. Provide workshops on academic writing, presentation skills, and effective communication for non-native speakers.
2. Organize social events to foster interactions between international and local students.
3. Facilitate peer mentoring (with the name ‘buddy’ and ‘ 선배 ‘ respectively in English and Korean), pairing experienced students with newcomers to ease their transition into university life.
4. Advocate for language inclusivity in classrooms and university events.
5. Hosting free volunteer English and Korean classes in both online and offline formats to improve the language efficiency of University staff.

The club will also collaborate with the university administration to suggest improvements to existing support systems, such as increasing access to language resources and cultural integration programs.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from Ajou University’s International Relations Committee. Participants were fully informed about the purpose of the study, and consent was obtained before interviews. To ensure confidentiality, all responses are anonymized, and participants' identities are protected.

Outcome

The findings from this study will inform not only the creation of the " Ajou Community" club but also potential policy recommendations for university staff and administration. By addressing language and social barriers, this research and newly launched club aims to foster a more inclusive and supportive campus environment for international students at Ajou University in Tashkent and in Korea.

Discussion

Overview of Key Findings

The findings from the interviews with 13 international students at Ajou University in Tashkent reveal several recurring themes regarding language barriers in a multinational academic setting:

- *Academic Challenges:* Many participants highlighted difficulties grasping lectures delivered in English or the host country's native language(which is Uzbek). Specific struggles included note-taking, completing assignments, working with groups, and participating in

discussions. One participant remarked, *“I feel like I understand the general idea, but when professors start speaking quickly, I lose track of everything.”* Another one said, *“When professors switch to Uzbek during class discussions, I feel left out because I can’t contribute effectively. It’s challenging to be part of group work or even ask questions without feeling out of place.”*

- **Social Isolation:** Language barriers also impede social integration. Students reported feeling excluded during informal gatherings where the host country’s language predominates. As one interviewee stated, *“It’s really hard to approach people when you know they’ll switch back to their language after a few minutes.”* Additionally, there were comments like, *“In informal settings, like group study sessions or social events, I often hear people speaking in Uzbek or English, and I just don’t understand everything they’re saying. It makes it hard to join in conversations or meet new people.”* , *“When everyone switches to the host country’s language after a few minutes, it becomes difficult to participate or maintain friendships. I sometimes feel like an outsider.”*

- **Lack of Institutional Support:** Students expressed frustration over the limited availability of language resources or structured programs to help international students adapt academically and socially. It was worth mentioning when one of the interviewees stated, *“There aren’t enough resources available to help international students improve their language skills. I wish there were more workshops or classes that focused on academic English and communication.”*, *“We need more structured programs that help us adjust to both the academic and social aspects of university life. Right now, it feels like we’re left to figure things out on our own.”*

Comparison with Literature

These findings align with existing research that highlights the influence of language barriers on international students' academic performance and social integration. For instance, Smith et al. (2019) argue that linguistic challenges often lead to diminished classroom participation and feelings of alienation, which our study also corroborates. However, unlike studies conducted in Western contexts, which often highlight the role of English proficiency alone, participants in this study at Ajou University emphasized challenges arising from the use of the host country’s native language in informal settings. This adds a unique cultural dimension to the existing body of knowledge.

Implications for the University

The results underscore the importance of Ajou University in Tashkent addressing these barriers to foster a more inclusive campus environment. Improving the academic and social experiences of international students not only enhances their academic success but also strengthens the university’s reputation as a global institution. The proposed student-run club, "Ajou Community," will directly address these issues by creating tailored workshops and providing peer mentorship. This initiative has the potential to bridge the gap between international and local students, promoting inclusivity and mutual understanding.

Future Research

Working on these findings, future studies could explore:

- A comparative analysis of language barriers faced by international students in other Uzbek and Korean universities such as Inha, Buchon, and Yaju International Korean Universities located in Tashkent.
- Longitudinal studies assessing the effectiveness of clubs like "Ajou Community" in improving academic and social outcomes.

- The role of technology, such as language learning apps or virtual mentoring platforms launched with the companionship of Ajou students from the Electrical Engineering Department in mitigating linguistic and cultural challenges.

Conclusion

This paper and thesis focus on the anthropological and sociological issues of students who are from a different country and are studying at Ajou University in Tashkent, particularly regarding their language of intercultural communication. The study was carried out through interviews with 13 students from various cultural and linguistic settings and reveals common difficulties in comprehending academic language, engaging in social activities, and functioning in a setting where the majority language is that of the host country.

These results highlight the need for educational institutions to eliminate such constructs with international students not only for their better integration but also to have a decent and globally competitive university ecosystem. The suggestions from the research, which seek to address these issues, include the development of specialized academic assistance services, organized cultural events, better language skills of university employees, and introduction of mentorship programs. The establishment of the club 'Ajou Community', which is in the early stages of implementing the project, is also one of the practical results of this study. It is expected that this institution will help to meet the needs of international students both socially and academically. The club intends to address the rift between international and local students through the means of a cohesive community and systemic advocacy that allows collaboration and understanding among members within a campus setting. In this regard, this study recognizes its limitations but also definitely points future researchers to what they may do further including undertaking comparative research across the universities or looking at vice versa. All these efforts and investments made in resolving the issues that international students grapple with are more than just an effort focused on the inclusion agenda but are a wise consideration for the growth and visibility of the university internationally. Such educational institutions as Ajou University have to focus on complementing investment with linguistic and cultural efforts so that their international students can excel academically and socially, thus creating a thriving and diverse environment on campus and working for the progress of their students.

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